

The teachings of Nina beyond the technical skills

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Abstract: I discovered the name of Nina Thornhill studying her topics of research in order to solve practical problems for my former job. Surely her work helped me initially as a practitioner in his early career, nonetheless her teaching goes beyond the technical skills. Being a person who needs a good working environment to feel good, I appreciated her mainly as person than as a simple teacher, because she is inspiring for the philosophy behind her research and the vision she had, for her leadership skills, optimism and energy.

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I am not a chemical engineer, I did not know what a distillation column is, how a valve is made, how many control tuning rules exist in process control engineering, the only reaction I knew was that oxygen and hydrogen form water, and no, I am sorry, I did not know Nina when I was a fresh graduated. However, knowing her and starting working with her has made the period of my PhD one of the most interesting of my life so far despite some personal problems out of our control. Probably because I am getting older, I start finding interesting linking the dots of my past and in this case reflecting how I got to know her.

It happened that the first job I obtained was in a chemical production site where I had to tune the PID controllers and implement the MPCs to optimise the plant operations. Despite the retuning of the controllers in a plant, one of first problems I faced was that “everything” in the plants was oscillating. I had initially no idea of the reasons of these phenomena (the plant-wide disturbances) and the colleagues had honestly less ideas than me. Their approach to process control was using Excel tables implementing tuning rules copied from somewhere and not fully understood. Using more rigorous principle was apparently ridiculous because “apparently” theory never works in practice. I did not and still I do not agree with this approach. Phenomena occurring in a real plant are certainly complex but for this reason they must be fully understood to be solved. This not only pushed me to further study and finally discover the name of Nina but also explains why I like the type of research she does.

I solved my first case of propagating disturbances tuning the controller without “tuning rules of Excel” rather like a control engineer would do. This approach helped initially me to solve many problems faced in the plant. However, I discovered with experience that not all problems are purely related to control. Studying some papers on the topic of plant-wide disturbances, the work of Nina was recurrently cited, and that is how I discovered her name.

The book ‘Diagnosis of process nonlinearities and valve stiction’ that she co-edited has been a game changer for me as

an early professional practitioner. It was not a theoretical book, rather an advanced practical book. Interpreting the disturbance patterns to identify the presence of a valve stiction or of a control problem, using phase space plots to diagnose valve stictions, adjusting the integral time of a controller to compensate valve nonlinearities were some of the basic things I have learnt from that book and that none of my colleagues knew after working for years in a plant. Most importantly, such methods were simple to use and they worked. Probably this book pushed me to give a change to my career, starting a PhD and learning from the applied research world.

I started my PhD with Nina because I was interested in her area of research but, honestly, I did not know the person initially. Nonetheless, knowing her after some months and years is one of the reasons that made the period of my PhD one of the most enjoyable I had.

In one of the first occasions, I asked her whether we should call her ‘Prof. Thornhill’ or ‘Nina’. Her answer was ‘You can call me as you prefer. The funny thing is when the students are undecided and start an email with prof. Nina’. Such answer, that showed an easy going and self-confident character, was for me a sort of nice revolution. Although I like a collaborative and informal working environment, I had been called for three years by surname by my former boss and by few former colleagues.

Later I discovered and appreciated the type career she did. Starting in a company, moving in academia but still closely collaborating with companies, she represented a bridge between academia and practice that society often blames it does not exist. With regards to this, I remember that, setting the programme for my PhD at its beginning, she suggested to not follow some ideas I had because they were hardly implementable and not user friendly for the real environment in a company. Probably this mind-set created the type of work I appreciated before as practitioner. Furthermore, there might be a teaching. If we want that our research is of any help for the society we should not produce whatever new

ideas rather we should aim to ideas that might be effective and implementable at very least in the long term.

In the subsequent months, I started to know her better for her leadership style. First of all, her intellectual honesty is exemplar and she knows how much I like it. A story she and I like to remember is about a technical matter we were discussing once. I said what I understood of the topic. She replied with another explanation. I replied back. She replied back. I gave up thinking that time would prove me right. However, I would have not thought that I had to wait only until the evening, when I received a piece of email from her, stating that I was right as she found a tutorial giving my same explanation. The situation was too funny and it has never occurred to me that my former bosses admitted they were wrong. Of course, it happened that she was right and I was wrong in other situations but the key teaching from her is that problems and not people must be faced during discussions. Therefore, being wrong from time to time is nothing to be ashamed of.

Furthermore, she showed me during these years an optimistic way of persuading and working with people. While I can be unfortunately pessimistic and critical against myself and others, she is always able to find good aspects of a whatever issue, to find a praise for the people she works with, she can put herself in the shoes of the interlocutor, fully understanding his/her issues and she can find a solution. I found this behaviour interesting in managing big groups with

different behaviours and interests. Especially in meetings with big groups she was able to always find common points and shared decisions, whereas that would be hard for me. Finally, it is admirable how active she is, attending several meetings and able to relocate from one country to another easily. For me, that I am already starting losing energy, this is a strong example.

I hope I can apply these teachings for the future and thank you, Nina.

Francesco

REFERENCES

- Borghesan, F., Chioua, M., & Thornhill, N. F. (2018). Forecast of persistent disturbances using k-nearest neighbour methods. In *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering* (Vol. 44, pp. 631-636). Elsevier.
- Borghesan, F., Chioua, M., & Thornhill, N. F. (2018, June). An MPC with disturbance forecasting for the control of the level of a tank with limited buffer capacity. In *2018 26th Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED)* (pp. 1-9). IEEE.
- Borghesan, F., Chioua, M., & Thornhill, N. F. (2019). Forecasting of process disturbances using k-nearest neighbours, with an application in process control. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 128, 188-200.